

Job Description Development in Fulfillment of the Competence of Village Government Apparatus (A Study in Banyumas Regency)

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ABSTRACT: A job description is a document containing the functions, duties, responsibilities, authorities, working conditions, and work implementation mechanism. The job description is quite important both for leader and employee, since with this document, they may clearly identify the competence they must meet for their position, with which employee's professionalism will eventually be built. The result of previous research in Banyumas Regency shows a gap between the competence of the village government apparatus and their position's standard competence. One of the reasons is an ineffective job description, which means there is no job description arranged entirely and in detail. Local Regulation of Banyumas Regency Number 1 the Year 2016 on the Structure and Working Procedure of Village Government only regulates the main duties and functions, not the job description. This Local Regulation actually mandates the village government to arrange the job description, but in reality, the village government has not performed it. Meanwhile, the village government's workload gets bigger and more varied since assignments are given by the ministry, provincial government, and regency government. Consequently, the village government apparatuses in Banyumas Regency do not know exactly what competencies they must have to implement their duties and position well. Therefore, this research aims at developing an effective job description for the positions of village government apparatus in Banyumas Regency. This survey research aims at describing the duties of village government apparatus positions comprehensively. The research successfully develops the job description of village government apparatus positions, covering the village head with 25 duties, village secretary with 16 duties, administrative and general coordinator with 14 duties, a financial coordinator with 9 duties, planning coordinator with 9 duties, governance section head with 11 duties, welfare section head with 10 duties, service section head with 9 duties and sub-village head with 5 duties.

KEYWORDS: Job Description, Village Government Apparatus, Village Government Apparatus Position.

INTRODUCTION

In the concept of human resource, the term job description refers to a document containing a summary of important information regarding office duties for ease of distinguishing one office duty from the other in an organization. This document also describes the functions, responsibilities, authorities and work conditions, including how to implement the duties to achieve the organization's objective effectively and efficiently. Job description is a very strategic part in explaining a work. Leader and employee are facilitated in understanding their contents of work. Such clear work limitation allows each employee to know exactly the competence they are supposed to meet in performing their work duties. This will finally realize employee's professionalism, efficiency and effectiveness in the organization.

Job description is the outcome of position analysis, which is a systematic attempt to collect, record, assess, analyze, organize and describe all kinds of work in an organization. Based on the job description produced, the characteristics of individual appropriate to a work duty implementation may be formulated. These characteristics are called job specification. Job specification is the minimum requirements an employee must meet for him to implement the work duties. These requirements cover certain qualification competence. The concerned qualification includes educational level, field of knowledge, work experience, training, etc. Meanwhile, competence covers knowledge, skill, attitude and behavior that an employee must have.

Job description is quite important to village government apparatus, considering that village government apparatus's workload after the implementation of Law Number 6 Year 2014 on Village gets heavier. Village government is given authority and responsibility not only for implementing, but also regulating its administration pursuant to village potential and its people's aspirations. The result of previous research in Banyumas Regency (Wahyuningrat, 2019) shows that there is a gap between the

competence of village government apparatus and their position's standard competence. This condition is due to ineffective job description of village government apparatus positions, that it lacks of description of real duties to be implemented by village government apparatus. There is difference between office duties formulated in the document and those actually implemented by village government apparatus. An ineffective job description causes village government apparatus not to understand what competence they are supposed to have and develop. If this is left as is, the professionalism of village government apparatus will not be built, which will eventually lead to worsening performance of village government. Based on the foregoing, this research aims at developing an effective job description for the positions of village government apparatus in Banyumas Regency.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Job Analysis

Job analysis is a process of collecting, analyzing and determining information of a work to generate job description and job specification (Armstrong, 2014; Daryanto and Abdulah, 2013; Dessler 2013). Job analysis attempts to identify a work to examine the duties, knowledge, skill, capability and other attributes the work needs. This is one method in human resource management related to the effort to identify and analyze the requirements needed for a work. In addition, it also analyzes individual needed for the work, thus the human resource chosen is actually capable of implementing the work duties (Tanumihardjo, 2013). Job analysis produces 3 (three) kinds of output simultaneously, namely job description, job specification and job evaluation. Job description is related to detailed description of the work, job specification is related to the requirements for individual who is going to implement the work duties and job evaluation is related to the grade of workload of the work. The three are directed to improving employee's performance and organization's efficiency and effectiveness (Sharif et al., 2017; Siddique, 2004).

The importance of job analysis is greatly felt by a manager since job analysis is a managerial instrument which greatly affects business process. It may evidently improve communication, accommodate changes and contribute to improved quality of human resource management and cost saving (Clifford, 1994; Prien, Prien & Wooten, 2003; Gatewood & Field, 1994). Job analysis presents informational base to various organizations and managerial functions, such as selection and personnel (Jenkins & Griffith, 2004), training and development (Campbell, 1989; Wooten, 1993), performance assessment (Latham & Fry, 1988), compensation and allowance (Taber & Peters, 1991; Weinberger, 1989), job description and job design (Konczak, 2007) and justice and affirmation program (Taggar & Smith, 2007; Thacker, 1990). Job analysis will be quite helpful for human resource manager to arrange future planning. Job specification as one of the outcomes of job analysis in combination with labor affairs law will be the base of decision making for human resource planning (Stoilkovska & Serafimovic, 2017; Lunenburg, 2012).

Job Description and Position Competence

Job description is a written document of what an employee who holds a work should to and explains the duties and responsibilities, work condition, work relation and work aspects of a certain position in an organization (Raju & Banerjee, 2017; Hasibuan, 2005; Mustikawati & Kurniawan, 2014; Rivai, 2009; Jackson, 2001). The existence of job description is quite important, since it will help employee improve his performance. An employee will have the direction of the main duties and functions of his job. An unclear job description will cause an employee not to understand of his authorities and responsibilities, since his work implementation will not run appropriately. If a job description is made well, it will prevent unnecessary misunderstanding by informing employee of what he needs to know of his work (Syelviani, 2017; Raju & Banerjee, 2017). Job description is the core of human resource management functions such as recruitment, performance evaluation, compensation and succession (Levine et al, 1988; Bodnarchuk, 2012).

Job description presents express and standard duties to be achieved by an employee. In addition, it may also serve as the base to determine job specification and job evaluation (Syelviani, 2017; Suryani et al., 2018). This shows that job description is the base for determining the competence an employee who holds a position must have. With a clear job description, the competence which is needed for the position and must be met by the position holder will be clearer. Competence covers knowledge, skill, experience, value and other attribute. Effective competence is a competence built from an overview of a job, namely job description. Observed from the beginning, job analysis is the process of generating a complete and clear picture of information of a job (job description). Meanwhile, job description is the base of building competence needed for the concerned job (Mustikawati & Kurniawan, 2014; Sharif & Karim, 2017). This interrelation may be observed in figure 1.

Figure 1. Interrelation of Job Analysis, Job description & Competence

RESEARCH METHOD

Pursuant to the research objective of developing an effective job description for village government apparatus positions, the type of this research is exploratory research. The research data consisted of primary data, from structured questionnaire and observation, and secondary data, from legislation, manual, statistical data and report. The research samples were determined using a multistage sampling technique, from determining sample village and village government apparatus samples. The data were collected from structured questionnaire with Likert's attitude scale. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistic technique to depict the information of village government apparatus positions.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Job Description of Village Government Apparatus in Normative Perspective

Job description of village government apparatus is normatively regulated through Regulation of Minister of Home Affairs Number 84 Year 2015 on the Organizational Structure and Working Procedure of Village Government. This regulation only regulates the main duties and functions of village government apparatus covering village head, village secretary, administrative and general coordinator, financial coordinator, planning coordinator, governance section head, welfare section head, service section head and sub-village head positions. Meanwhile, in Banyumas Regency, the job description of village government apparatus is regulated through Local Regulation of Banyumas Regency Number 1 Year 2016 on the Organizational Structure and Working Procedure of Village Government. The Local Regulation also only regulates the main duties and functions of each position, which are almost the same with what is explained in the Regulation of Minister of Home Affairs. Therefore, there is no regulation which presents job description for village government apparatus positions. The Local Regulation has indeed mandated head of village government to arrange job description, but in fact the village governments have not arranged their job description.

Main duties and functions may indeed be used as the guidance for village government apparatus to implement their office duties, but are quite general. Main duties and functions have not explained information of job in detail as expected by (Raju & Banerjee, 2017; Mustikawati & Kurniawan, 2014), that job description must explain completely and in detail the duties, responsibilities, work condition, work relation, facilities and infrastructure needed, to office performance target. This is similar to what is delivered by Haris (2018), that most of Civil Servants in Sarudu Subdistrict, North Mamuju Regency do not have good performance since they do not understand their main duties and functions. Main duties and functions have not explained in detail the duties an employee must perform; thus, they are not easily understood. Differently, job description has explained in detail and specifically each of the duties along with the authorities, responsibilities, work relation, facilities and infrastructure, and work environment condition.

Non-existing job description makes village government apparatuses in Banyumas Regency hardly understand their duties; thus, they do not know what competences they should have to implement their duties well. Job description for village government

apparatus in Banyumas Regency is quite important since after the implementation of Law Number 6 Year 2014 on Village, village government is assigned with very heavy duties. The duties are not only from the Ministry of Home Affairs, but also from the Ministry of Villages, Development of Disadvantaged Regions, and Transmigration, Provincial Government of Central Java and Government of Banyumas Regency. Employee’s unawareness of the competences they must have because the duties to be performed are greatly varied and changing and have not been expressed in a job description (Pitaloka et al., 2019; Bodnarchuk, 2012). Therefore, the development of job description with village government apparatus offices is quite urgent.

Development of Job Description of Village Government Apparatus Positions

The development of job description of village government apparatus positions starts with identifying duties actually implemented by village government apparatus. The duties are implemented based on what authority and responsibility, how to implement it, what facilities and infrastructure should be available for good performance of duties, and in what working environmental condition. The result of identification is then compared to the main duties and functions designated both in Regulation of Minister of Home Affairs Number 84 Year 2016 and Local Regulation Banyumas Regency Number 1 Year 2016. Based on the comparison, an effective job description is then developed actually pursuant to the real condition implemented by village government apparatus. The comparison and result of development of job description may be observed in table 1.

Table 1. Comparison of Main Duties Based on Local Regulation with the Result of Identification of the Implementation of Duties and Job Description Development

Village Government Apparatus Position	Local Regulation of Banyumas Regency No. 1 Year 2016	Result of Identification of Duty Implementation	Job Description Development
Village Head	1. Administer village administration 2. Implement development in the village 3. Guide village society 4. Empower village society 5. Maintain partnership connection	1. Public administrative management duty 2. Regulatory duty 3. Land affair duty 4. Public serenity and order duty 5. Community protection duty 6. Population and data duty 7. Area management duty 8. Education, facility and infrastructure and health development duty 9. Community fostering and partnership connection duty 10. Cultural preservation duty 11. Labor affair duty	1. Administer public administrative management 2. Administer drafting village regulation 3. Administer stipulation of village regulation 4. Administer land affair guidance 5. Administer public serenity and order guidance 6. Administer community protection effort 7. Administer population administrative affairs 8. Administer area arrangement and management 9. Administer village profile data acquisition 10. Administer village profile management 11. Administer village facilities-infrastructure development 12. Administer education development 13. Administer health development 14. Administer community’s right and obligation guidance 15. Administer outreach of community’s right and obligation implementation 16. Administer motivation for community’s right and obligation implementation 17. Administer improved effort of public participation 18. Administer partnership connection guidance

			<p>19. Administer social community value preservation</p> <p>20. Administer cultural value preservation</p> <p>21. Administer religious value preservation</p> <p>22. Administer labor value preservation</p> <p>23. Administer community empowerment in the form of community socialization and motivation in culture and politics</p> <p>24. Administer community empowerment in the form of community socialization and motivation in youth affairs, sports and youth organization;</p> <p>25. Administer community empowerment in the form of community socialization and motivation in economy, family empowerment and environment.</p>
Village Secretary	<p>1. Coordinate section heads' duties and functions</p> <p>2. Implement administrative affairs</p> <p>3. Implement general affairs</p> <p>4. Implement financial affairs</p> <p>5. Implement planning affairs</p>	<p>1. Coordination duty</p> <p>2. Governmental duty</p> <p>3. Administrative duty</p> <p>4. General duty</p> <p>5. Manuscript duty</p> <p>6. Correspondence duty</p> <p>7. Archiving duty</p> <p>8. Forwarding duty</p> <p>9. Village apparatus arrangement duty</p> <p>10. Duty related to village apparatus's infrastructure</p> <p>11. Meeting arrangement duty</p> <p>12. Village asset management duty</p> <p>13. Official travel administrative duty</p> <p>14. Internal service and control duty.</p>	<p>1. Implement village head assisting duty in government and administration</p> <p>2. Implement village apparatus coordination</p> <p>3. Implement administrative affairs</p> <p>4. Implement general administrative affairs</p> <p>5. Implement manuscript administration</p> <p>6. Implement correspondence administration</p> <p>7. Implement archiving and forwarding administration</p> <p>8. Implement village apparatus administrative arrangement</p> <p>9. Implement administration of provision of village apparatus infrastructure and office</p> <p>10. Implement meeting activity administration</p> <p>11. Implement administration of strategic village asset</p> <p>12. Implement administration of village's other assets</p> <p>13. Implement inventorying administration</p> <p>14. Implement official travel administration</p> <p>15. Implement public service administration</p> <p>16. Implement administration of village government's internal control system.</p>
Administrative and General Coordinator	<p>Implement administrative affairs, including document management, correspondence, archiving and forwarding administration, village</p>	<p>1. Administrative material preparation duty</p> <p>2. Preparing material of general affairs duty</p> <p>3. Preparing material of document management duty</p>	<p>1. Prepare material in administrative affairs implementation</p> <p>2. Prepare material in general affairs implementation</p> <p>3. Prepare material in document management implementation</p> <p>4. Prepare material in correspondence administration implementation</p>

	officials administration arrangement, procurement of infrastructure of village officials and office, meeting preparation, asset administration, inventorying, official travel and general services.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. Correspondence and forwarding administration duty 5. Archiving duty 6. Preparing material of village officials administration duty 7. Facilities and infrastructure procurement duty 8. Meeting material preparation duty 9. Preparing material of asset administration duty 10. Preparing material of official travel administration duty 11. Service material preparation duty 12. Internal control system preparation duty 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5. Prepare material in archiving and forwarding activities 6. Prepare material in village officials administration management 7. Prepare material in procurement of infrastructure of village officials and office 8. Prepare material in meeting activities 9. Prepare material in the administration of strategic village assets 10. Prepare material in the administration of village' other assets 11. Prepare material in inventorying affairs 12. Prepare material in official travel implementation 13. Prepare material in general services implementation 14. Prepare material in village government internal control system.
Financial Coordinator	Management of financial administration, administration of sources of income and expenditure, verification of financial administration, and administration of the income of Village Head, Village Officials, BPD and other village governmental institutions.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Preparing material of financial affairs duty 2. Preparing material of financial source administration duty 3. Preparing material of expenditure administration duty 4. Preparing material of financial administration verification duty 5. Preparing material of administration of village head's income duty 6. Preparing material of administration of village officials' income duty 7. Preparing material of administration of BPD's income duty 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Prepare material in financial affairs implementation 2. Prepare material in financial administration management implementation 3. Prepare material in income sources administration implementation 4. Prepare material in expenditure administration implementation 5. Prepare material in financial administration verification implementation 6. Prepare material in village head's income administration implementation 7. Prepare material in village officials' income administration implementation 8. Prepare material in BPD's income administration implementation 9. Prepare material in other village governmental institution's income administration implementation

<p>Planning Coordinator</p>	<p>Plan village budget, inventory data in concerning development, monitor and evaluate programs, and arrange report.</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Planning material preparation duty 2. Preparing material of budget plan arrangement duty 3. Preparing material for budget plan duty 4. Preparing material for inventorying data concerning development duty 5. Program monitoring and evaluation preparation duty 6. Reporting material preparation duty. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Prepare material in planning implementation 2. Prepare material in village budgeting 3. Prepare material in village budget planning 4. Prepare material in inventorying data regarding development 5. Prepare material in physical building administration 6. Prepare material in non-physical development administration 7. Prepare material in implementing monitoring program 8. Prepare material in program evaluation implementation 9. Prepare material in reporting.
<p>Governance Section Head</p>	<p>Implement governmental administration management, help Village Secretary in arranging draft village legal product, land affairs guidance, serenity and order guidance, implement the effort of society protection, demography, territorial arrangement and management, and data acquisition and management of village profile.</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Administrative management duty 2. Village regulation duty 3. Land guidance duty 4. Public serenity and order guidance duty 5. Society protection duty 6. Demographic duty 7. Territorial management duty 8. Duties related to village profile 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Technical implementation of administration of governmental administration management 2. Technical implementation of administration of village regulation drafting 3. Technical implementation of administration of village regulation stipulation 4. Technical implementation of administration of land affair guidance 5. Technical implementation of administration of public serenity and order guidance 6. Technical implementation of society protection effort 7. Technical implementation of demographic administration 8. Technical implementation of demographic administration 9. Technical implementation of administration of territorial arrangement and management 10. Technical implementation of administration of data acquisition of village profile 11. Technical implementation of administration of village profile management.
<p>Welfare Section Head</p>	<p>Implement development of village facilities and infrastructure, development of education, health and socialization and society motivation duties in culture,</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Facilities and infrastructure development duty 2. Education development duty 3. Health development duty 4. Cultural development duty 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Technical implementation of administration of village facilities-infrastructure development 2. Technical implementation of administration of education development 3. Technical implementation of administration of health development

	economy, politics, environment, family empowerment, youth, sports and youth organization.	5. Economic development duty 6. Political development duty 7. Environmental development duty 8. Empowerment duty 9. Youth and sports duty	4. Technical implementation of administration of socialization and society motivation duties in cultural sector 5. Technical implementation of administration of socialization and society motivation duties in economic sector 6. Technical implementation of administration of socialization and society motivation duties in political sector 7. Technical implementation of administration of socialization and society motivation duties in environmental sector 8. Technical implementation of administration of socialization and society motivation duties in family empowerment sector 9. Technical implementation of administration of socialization and society motivation duties in youth and sports sector 10. Technical implementation of administration of socialization and society motivation duties in youth organization sector.
Service Section Head	Implement counseling and motivation regarding community's right and obligation implementation, enhance public participation effort, preserve community socio-cultural, religious and labor values.	1. Community's right and obligation guidance duty 2. Public participation enhancement duty 3. Partnership connection guidance duty 4. Social values preservation duty 5. Religious values preservation duty 6. Labor values preservation duty	1. Technical implementation of community's right and obligation guidance administration 2. Technical implementation of counseling administration regarding community's right and obligation guidance 3. Technical implementation of motivational administration regarding community's right and obligation implementation 4. Technical implementation of enhancement of public participation effort 5. Technical implementation of partnership connection guidance administration 6. Technical implementation of community's social value preservation 7. Technical implementation of community's cultural value preservation 8. Technical implementation of religious value preservation 9. Technical implementation of labor value preservation.
Sub-village Head	1. Guidance of serenity and order, implement community protection effort, population mobility, and area	1. Area arrangement and management duty 2. Guidance of public serenity and order, community	1. Technical implementation of area arrangement and management 2. Technical implementation of guidance of public serenity and order, implementation of community protection effort, population

	<p>arrangement and management</p> <p>2. Supervise development implementation in relevant sub-village area</p> <p>3. Implement community guidance in improving community's ability and awareness of environmental protection</p> <p>4. Perform community empowerment efforts in support of smooth administration of village governance and village development</p>	<p>protection and population mobility duty</p> <p>3. Supervisory duty</p> <p>4. Environmental guidance duty</p> <p>5. Community empowerment duty</p>	<p>mobility, and area arrangement and management</p> <p>3. Technical implementation of supervision over development implementation in his area</p> <p>4. Technical implementation of community guidance in improvement of community's capability and awareness of environmental protection</p> <p>5. Technical implementation of community empowerment efforts in support of smooth administration of governance and development.</p>
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CONCLUSION

Based on the description above, we may conclude that developing the job description of village government apparatus in Banyumas Regency is quite important since from the normative perspective, job description is not available yet. Meanwhile, the volume of village government's assignments from the ministry, provincial government and regency government increases. Through job description development, even with heavier workload, but the duties village government apparatus must perform are clearly outlined. Therefore, village government apparatus will understand the competences they need to have better for their office duties to be well implemented.

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REFERENCES

1. Armstrong, M. (2014). *A Handbook of Human Resource Management Practice*. Published by Kogan Page Limited United Kingdom. Page 29
2. Bodnarchuk, M. (2012). The Role of Job Description and Competencies in International Organizations: Case: Foster Wheeler Energia Oy. *Bachelor's Thesis*
3. Campbell, J.P. (1989). *Modeling The Performance Prediction Problem in Industrial and Organizational Psychology*. Palo Alto: Consulting Psychologists Press
4. Clifford, P. (1994). The Relationship between Job Satisfaction and Performance, The Case Local Government Finance Officers in Ohio. *Public Productivity & Management Review*. Vol 21 No. 2
5. Daryanto & Abdullah. (2013). *Pengantar Ilmu Manajemen dan Komunikasi*. Jakarta: Prestasi Pustaka
6. Dessler, G. (2013). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Edisi 10. Jakarta: Indeks
7. Gatewood, R.D., & Field, H.S. (1994). *Human Resource Selection*. Ohio: South Western Learning
8. Haris, Abdul. (2018). Analisis Kinerja Pegawai Berdasarkan Tugas Pokok dan Fungsi Pada Kantor Kecamatan Sarudu Kabupaten Mamuju Utara. *Jurnal Katalogis*. Vol 6. No. 3. P 1-19
9. Hasibuan, Malayu S.P., (2005). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Jakarta: Bumi Aksara
10. Levine, E.L., Sistrunk, F., McNutt, K.J., & Gael, S. (1988). Exemplary Job Analysis Systems in Selected Organizations: A Description of Process and Outcomes. *Journal of Business and Psychology*. Vol 3. P 3-21

11. Lunenburg, F.C. (2012). Human Resource Planning: Forecasting Demand and Supply. *International Journal of Management, Business, and Administration*. Vol 15 Issue 1. P 1-10
12. Mustikawati, F., Kurniawan, I. (2014). Pengaruh Job Description Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Departemen Security di PT. Wilmar Nabati Indonesia-Gresik. *Gema Ekonomi Jurnal Fakultas Ekonomi*. Vol 3. No. 2. P 154-180
13. Pitaloka, K., Mulyatini, N., Kasman. (2019). Pengaruh Job Description, Job Specification Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan (Suatu Studi Pada PT. Pos Indonesia Cabang Ciamis). *Business Management and Entrepreneurship Journal*. Vol 1. No 2. P 42-58
14. Prien, K.O., Prien, E.P., Wooten, W. (2003). Interrater Reliability in Job Analysis: Differences in Strategy and Perspective. *Journal Public Personnel Management*. Vol 32. P 125-141
15. Raju, K.K. Banerjee, S. (2017). A Study on Job Description and Its Effect on Employee Performance: Case of Some Selected Manufacturing Organizations in the City of Pune, India. *International Journal of Latest Technology in Engineering, Management & Applied Science*. Vol VI. Issue II
16. Rivai, Veithzal. (2009). Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia untuk Perusahaan dari Teori ke Praktik. Jakarta: Raja Grafindo Persada
17. Sharif, A.M., Karim, M. (2017). Influence of Job Analysis Program on Employees: A Study on Selected Companies of Bangladesh. *International Journal of Scientific and Engineering Research*. Vol 8 Issue 5. P 1221-1225
18. Siddique, C.M. (2004). Job Analysis: A Strategic Human Resource Management Practice. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*. Vol 15 Issue 1. P 219-244
19. Stoilkovska, A. Serafimovic, G. (2017). Job Analysis as an Important Human Resources Management Function. *International Refereed Scientific Journal Vision*. Vol 2 Issue 1. P 113-124
20. Suryani, I.M., Sulistyaningrum, C.D., Murwaningsih, T. (2018). Analisis Penerapan Job Description Pegawai (Studi Kasus Di Pengadilan Negeri Surakarta Kelas IA Khusus). *Jurnal Informasi dan Komunikasi, Administrasi Perkantoran*. Vol 2. No. 5
21. Syelviani, M. (2017). Pengaruh Deskripsi Jabatan Terhadap Kinerja Pegawai Negeri Sipil Pada Kantor Camat Tembilahan. *Journal of Economy, Business and Accounting (Costing)*. Vol 1 No. 1. P 43-55
22. Tanumihardjo, Shinta. (2013). Pengaruh Analisis Jabatan Terhadap Kinerja Pegawai (Studi Pada Sekretariat Daerah Pemerintah Kabupaten Malang). *Jurnal Administrasi Publik (JAP)*. Vol 1. No. 6. P 1114-1122
23. Wahyuningrat. (2019). Pengembangan Sumber Daya Aparatur Pemerintah Desa Berbasis Kompetensi Menuju Desa Unggul Mandiri di Kabupaten Banyumas. Laporan Penelitian. LPPM Unsoed

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